

“Leadership and Challenges” An Empirical Study on Economic Growth in the Field of Financial Technology in the Present Era

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 2

Month: November

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2321-788X

E-ISSN: 2582-0397

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Akshatha, BH, and R. Umamaheshwari. “Leadership and Challenges’ An Empirical Study on Economic Growth in the Field of Financial Technology in the Present Era.” *Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science & Humanities*, vol. 7, no. S2, 2019, pp. 253–55.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3575351>

BH. Akshatha & R. Umamaheshwari

3rd Semester M.Com, Sri Aurobindo College

Abstract

Finance plays a significant role in the world. Technology in the finance field has made tremendous changes in the economy. Without adopting innovation strategies, companies will lose their competitive advantage in an increasingly commoditized world. There is no limit to lose, as technology change accelerates exponentially, and new digital platforms and devices are emerging. Then the expectations of the new generation are such that companies must keep up with the pace of change or lose relevance. They adopt their lifestyles to each new technological invention, and in the midst of all this, we need to keep in mind the problems of digital change such as customer relationship, increased competition, and constant digital engagement with the consumer. These paper technological inventions have revolutionized each sector of society by reducing human labor, bringing efficiency, and increasing productivity. This research is a stepping stone in exploring the interaction between Fintech.

Fintech the word which originates from “finance” and “technology”, designates currently a novel, innovate, and emerging field which attracts attention from the publicity. Though this paper, we also identify drivers of financial technology and put them in the context of Fintech innovation research. By this we provide an objective understanding of Fintech, how it is reflected in popular media. As technology is a key driver of growth for the banking sector in India. The emergency of Fintech is beginning to disrupt the financial world with transformative changes. The unique consumer behavior and banking habits of people, coupled with their pro-technology attitude, facilitate the rapidly advancing disruptive revolution of Fintech. Banks and financial institutions alike have been adopting innovative technology to cater to the ubiquitous use of mobile devices. As many Fintech companies accelerate their customers with more convenient financial services experience at much lower costs.

Keywords: Financial Technology, Competitive Advantage, Efficiency, Convenient, Digital, Revolution.

Introduction

Fintech is a combination of the terms “finance” and “technology” and refers to any business that uses technology to enhance or automate financial services and processes. This is a broad and rapidly growing industry serving both consumers and business. From mobile banking to investment apps, Fintech has huge applications. One driving factor is that many traditional banks are supporters and adopters of technology, actively investing in, or acquiring with Fintech startups because it is easier to give tech-savvy customers

what they want, while also moving the industry forward and staying pertinent. Customers expect everything to be effortless, reliable, and more secure without the assistance of anyone or personal visit to any banks. Compared to traditional banks, Fintech Startups operate flexibly and adopt new kinds of services based on consumer demands. In a country like India, the Fintech market is expected to grow 1.7 billion times by 2020. Huge investments are pooled from foreign and native companies with the objective of creating a cashless society.

The Objectives of the Study

- To study the concept of financial services and usage
- To know the benefits and usage of financial services packages for the companies
- To understand the challenges of financial services
- To provide suggestions for adopting financial services

Research Methodology

Secondary data- a publication from various websites, journals, research papers, surveys which focused on different aspects of Fintech.

Impact of Technology in Financial Services

Technology has changed the complete perspective of the financial sector's operations. Globalization and liberalization have forced banks to think in terms of technology benefits and quality service to customers as the future is full of challenges and survival will be a difficult task. The tilt in the banks from traditional to modern banking services has been welcomed due to its advantages. It is becoming increasingly clear that technology alone can enable bankers to navigate through the competition. Developing intelligent digital assistants, providing seamless services and building data models, acting on leading decisions, and enhancing customer relationship, security with the advanced recognition techniques are a few ways by which bankers use technology today to beat the competition.

The concept of Fintech has enabled the banking organizations to redesign and restructure their functioning.

Loans: Granting loans and related services can be easily used by the consumers.

Payment gateways: It is a new means by which the bank facilitates the payments by directly debiting the bank accounts or by using credit cards or with the help of smart phones.

Investment plans: Financial technology helps in comparing and gives good investment plans for personal finance.

Foreign Transactions: It has become very simple and affordable, especially in case of remittance transfers.

Insurance: Getting insurance services has now become a less complex procedure.

Financial Markets: Maintenance and collection of shares, determination of price, calculation of returns with the help of demat account is very easy.

New Technology: Technology like artificial intelligence (AI), block chain, cryptography, and biometrics have made big data management very simple.

The Challenges of Financial Technology

Knowledge: Many users are unaware of the financial technology and still prefer to stick on to the old traditional form of banking.

Trust: Many customers do not trust these technologies because of sensitive financial information, which they consider risky.

Security: It is one of the biggest threats of Fintech industry. Password cracking and cyber-attacks are common drawbacks of adopting financial technology.

Human Resource: Fintech is also a biggest threat to human resource and employment because of introduction of AI and chat-bots which are expected to replace human beings.

Training to staff: Business must focus on providing skill development and training to its staff regarding financial technology.

References

1. <http://www.academia.edu/Documents/in/Fintech> https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Financial_technology <https://www.fintechweekly.com/fintech-definition>.
2. <https://www.investopedia.com/ask/answers/030315/what-financial-services-sector.asp>.
3. <https://financialservices.gov.in/>.
4. <https://www.siliconindia.com/news/general/Impact-of-fintech-in-India-nid-204284-cid-1.htm>